

Kuzikova Svitlana, Shcherbak Tetiana
Sumy State Pedagogical University named after A.S. Makarenko, Sumy
CONTENT ANALYSIS of EXPERIENCES of WAR TRAUMA of
RESIDENTS of DEOCCUPIED REGIONS of UKRAINE*

Кузікова С.Б., Щербак Т.І.

Сумський державний педагогічний університет імені

А.С.Макаренка, м. Суми

ЗМІСТОВИЙ АНАЛІЗ ПЕРЕЖИВАНЬ ТРАВМ ВІЙНИ МІШКАНЦІВ
ДЕОКУПОВАНИХ ОБЛАСТЕЙ УКРАЇНИ*

Статтю присвячено проблемі інтегративного підходу до визначення особливостей переживання множинних травм російсько-української війни. Досліджуваним незалежно від віку властиві такі травми війни як відокремленість від членів сім'ї, численні смерті членів родини і друзів, зруйновані будинки та смерть домашніх тварин; найбільше травми війни вплинули на систему цінностей та переконань підлітків та молоді, звідси, ми можемо констатувати наявність моральної травми, за відсутності симптомів ПТСР.

Ключові слова: *травматичний стрес, ПТСР, горе, втрата, війна, особистість.*

Psychological help and support of individuals in life crisis situations have always been the focus of attention of scientists and practitioners. However, the Russian-Ukrainian war, which became widespread in February 2022 and continues to this day, presented psychologists with new challenges, including the need to create their own system of psychological assistance for children and adults – victims of hostilities. This research is a pilot study, as it was implemented in the conditions of the existence of the threat of shelling on the territory of Kyiv, Sumy and Kharkiv regions.

To implement the research purpose, we used the following methods: Hospital Anxiety and Depression Scale (HADS, A. S. Zigmond and R. P. Snaith, 1983, adapted by A. V. Andrushchenko, 2003), the PCL-5 method (F. W. Weathers, B. T. Litz, T. M. Keane, 2013), HGRC, N. S. Hogan, 2001, Inventory of Social Support (ISS), N. S. Hogan, L. A. Schmidt, 2016). In this research, we compared the war trauma of persons aged 13 to 70 who were in the zone of active hostilities, left it through internal migration, and were in their cities and towns under temporary occupation (Kyiv, Sumy, Kharkiv regions of Ukraine).

*** тези доповідей на круглому столі «Актуальні проблеми психологічної практики та підготовки фахівців в умовах воєнного стану» (28.10.2022 р.)**

328 people took part in the research, of which 13-18 years old – 94 (28.66%), 19-30 years old – 66 (20.12%), 31-50 years old – 72 (21.95%), 51 -70 years old – 96 (32.27%). The average age of the subjects is 47.5±10.3 years; female – 206 (62.81%), male – 122 (37.19%).

Table 1

Features of PTSD symptoms of people of different ages according to the PCL-5 method; frequency analysis of traumatic events of the subjects

Indicators	13-18 years	19-30 years	31-50 years	51-70 years
Average values of severity of PTSD symptoms				
Intrusions (criterion B)	1,16	2,46	2,87	3,25**
Avoidance (criterion C)	2,19	2,38	2,32	2,94**
Negative alterations in cognition and mood (criterion D)	3,19**	0,29	1,19	1,08
Arousal (criterion E)	3,94**	2,06	2,18	3,67**
Frequency analysis of traumatic events (Criterion A)				
Moving to a worse place of residence	86 (91,49%)	42 (63,64%)	38 (57,78%)	12 (12,51%)
Ruined house	62 (65,96%)	36 (54,55%)	49 (68,05%)	74 (77,08%)
Humiliation in front of other people	3 (3,19%)	27 (40,91%)	18 (25,01%)	0
Torture	0	12 (18,19%)	9 (12,51%)	0
Separation from family members	92 (97,86%)	63 (95,45%)	51 (70,83%)	46 (47,92%)
Numerous deaths of family members	73 (77,65%)	62 (93,94%)	68 (94,44%)	42 (43,75%)
Seeing dead people on the streets, in houses that have been lying there for a long time	29 (30,84%)	57 (86,36%)	53 (73,61%)	37(38,54%)
Witnessing rape and other types of violence	1 (1,06%)	16 (24,23%)	11 (26,19%)	2 (2,08%)
Death of domestic animals	92 (97,88%)	59 (89,39%)	64 (88,89%)	83 (86,46%)

Note: ** – statistical significance of $p \leq 0,001$

First of all, we determined the features of the severity of PTSD symptoms according to the PTSD Checklist for DSM-5 (PCL-5) method. This questionnaire involves the calculation of points according to four criteria B (intrusions), C

(avoidance), D (negative alterations in cognition and mood) and E (arousal). In addition, the presence of criterion A (traumatic event) is established. The results of the study using the PCL-5 method are presented in the table 1, as well as the frequency analysis of traumatic events, which civilian witnesses, and sometimes combatants, identified as the most significant, those that can potentially cause stress disorders and PTSD.

Respondents between the ages of 13 and 18 are most likely to experience such war traumas as separation from family members, most often from their father, but often moving with siblings without both parents (97.86%); death of domestic animals (97.88%); moving to a worse place of residence (91.49%) and numerous deaths of family members and friends (77.65%). Persons aged 19 to 30 are most likely to experience such traumatic events: numerous deaths of family members (93.94%), separation from family members (95.45%), death of domestic animals (89.39%) and seeing dead people on the streets, in houses that have been lying there for a long time (86.36%). A similar situation is also observed in the subjects aged 31 to 50 years, for them the greatest psychological traumas were the numerous deaths of family members (94.44%) and the death of domestic animals (88.89%). The vast majority of older subjects did not leave their permanent residence, or left it for a short time, however, the most significant traumatic events for them were a destroyed house (77.08%) and the death of domestic animals (86.46%).

We note that teenagers and young people suffered the most war injuries, however, due to the available internal and external resources, they most effectively adapted to the situation that arose with them. A traumatic event (criterion A) is statistically significantly correlated only with criterion E (arousal), that is, we can state that a traumatic event causes irritability, increased excitability, alertness and sleep problems, but in general, the very fact of the presence of a traumatic event does not always cause the development of PTSD symptoms (since only one criterion E is not enough for its diagnosis).

The traumas of the war had the greatest impact on the system of values and beliefs of teenagers and young people, who for the first time in their lives came into contact with an uncontrolled and dangerous world, sometimes we can state the presence of moral trauma especially among young people. Moral trauma usually refers to the negative consequences for conscience when people commit, witness, or fail to prevent actions that conflict with their personal values and moral beliefs.

In contrast to psychopathology, moral damage is a normal human reaction to an abnormal traumatic event. In addition, for young people, as well as for older people (after 50 years), excitement was the main reaction to trauma, it is often expressed in panic behavior, inability to sleep (intensified by acoustic night terror), eating problems, in particular in adolescents after occupation, we repeatedly observed symptoms of bulimia. Symptoms of avoidance and intrusions are most characteristic of subjects over 50 years of age, on the other hand, PTSD

symptoms according to the PCL-5 method are not statistically significantly expressed in persons aged 19 to 50 years.

According to the HADS method in all age groups of the subjects subclinical anxiety was detected, the so-called borderline state, however, no symptoms of depression were observed in the subjects (we take into account the specificity of the research, which was conducted during the war, when the mobilization of all personal resources is maximal). Panic behavior, refers not only to panic attacks, which are also very characteristic of the respondents, but also to anxiety and psychosomatic symptoms, including headaches, stomachaches and backaches, which are more characteristic of young people and persons under 40 years of age, while despair is characteristic of all subjects, however, especially those over 50, for whom despair is positively correlated with arousal ($r=0.794$) and intrusions ($r=0.691$). Instead, guilt (guilt of a person who survived, escaped), anger and detachment are more characteristic of the researched age from 30 to 50 years, especially if they live in the rear, where there are isolated air alarms and there is no destruction due to rocket attacks.

We state that, conceptually, the Inventory of Social Support items represent the degree to which the grieving person perceives that there is at least one person who will take the time to unquestioningly listen to them while they sincerely and honestly express their thoughts and feelings about grief. There are statistically significant negative correlations of social support with PCL-5 indicators, particularly avoidance and intrusions, and with HADS depressive symptoms. Accordingly, depression and avoidance of traumatic events and grief are negatively associated with the availability of social support. The strongest relationship between social support and personal growth was set down 2.5 months after the loss, however, the person had already been in a war-free territory for a long time. In other words, social support reduces the intensity of grieving, thereby opening up opportunities for post-traumatic personality growth after it.

Therefore, regardless of age, such war traumas as separation from family members, numerous deaths of family members and friends, destroyed houses and the death of pets are characteristic of the subjects, regardless of age. The traumas of the war had the greatest impact on the system of values and beliefs of teenagers and young people, however, PTSD symptoms are more characteristic of the subjects over the age of 50, who have a lack of internal and external resources (social support). We have proven that the social support model we developed for combatants, with whom we worked from 2014-2020, is relevant for use with civilians of all ages in the current large-scale war. This model is based on successive post-traumatic periods, when the system of social ties expands: from the limited to the acute adaptation period, when the close environment performs almost all functions to the gradual differentiation of ties due to the inclusion in a group of individuals with a common traumatic experience as a member of this group in the adaptation period and other social groups in the resilient-integration period. We emphasize the need to research the best world practices of providing

psychological assistance to victims of war, and in the absence of them, to create and spread our own, since the experience of Ukraine is largely unique and will be useful for psychologists of various countries where armed conflicts are potentially likely, this task is an important prospect for further scientific research.